

Major weed species in several rice areas as ranked in importance by farmers. Madagascar, Nov 1990 and May 1992.

Weed species	Local name
Middle West ^a (Upland rice ecosystem)	
<i>Striga asiatica</i>	Arema
<i>Rottboellia cochinchinensis</i>	Tsaganday
<i>Acanthospermum hispidum</i>	Bakakely
<i>Urena lobata</i>	Kerijy
<i>Tridax procumbens</i>	Angamay Mahapady
<i>Digitaria setigera</i>	Marorantsana Fandroahy
North West (Rainfed lowland rice ecosystem)	
Tsararano, Marovoay	
<i>Cyperus difformis</i>	Somotrosy
<i>Cyperus iria</i>	Chipisoka
<i>Fimbristylis miliacea</i>	Sombengy
<i>Ludwigia adscendens</i>	Volondrano
<i>Paspalum distichum</i>	Menavavy
<i>Cynodon dactylon</i>	Fandotrarana
Mampikony	
<i>Aeschynomene indica</i>	Renaud
<i>Ludwigia octovalvis</i>	Ranjamena
<i>Brachiaria distachya</i>	Tergal
<i>Ischaemum rugosum</i>	Tsikababanga Tainbiriky
Port Berge	
<i>Sphenoclea zeylanica</i>	Bomata
<i>Fimbristylis miliacea</i>	Sombengy
<i>Aeschynomene indica</i>	Renaud
<i>Paspalum distichum</i>	Menavavy
<i>Cyperus difformis</i>	Somotrosy
<i>Cyperus rotundus</i>	Tsimitamita
<i>Echinochloa colona</i>	Tsivakimpanoto Ampody Tsifaryfary Tsikababanga Tainbiriky
<i>Ischaemum rugosum</i>	Tsikababanga Tainbiriky
Central Highland ^b (Rainfed lowland rice ecosystem)	
<i>Potamogeton fluitans</i>	Valatendro
<i>Scirpus juncooides</i>	Ahidratsy
<i>Leersia hexandra</i>	Tsiriry
<i>Echinochloa colona</i> ^c	Tsivakimpanoto Ampody Tsifaryfary Karangimena
<i>Echinochloa crus-galli</i> ^d	Karangimena

field after rice harvest were a problem during land preparation.

In Port Berge, *Sphenoclea zeylanica* was the major weed problem. Farmers considered it the most difficult to control because of its abundant growth.

Farmers in three villages of the Central Highland considered *Potamogeton fluitans* to be their worst weed. Control of *P. fluitans* requires

large amounts of hand weeding. Few farmers thought that the weed could be controlled by plowing and harrowing after rice harvest and subsequent drying during the dry season.

It was observed that farmers considered a weed important based on abundance in the field and difficulty of control. ■

Weed - fish interactions at different water levels in irrigated ricefields in Northeast Thailand

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We conducted a field trial on eight farms in the Lam Dom Noi irrigated area in Ubon Province, Northeast Thailand, in the 1987 dry season. Each farmer provided two rice - fish fields and two control fields that were 0.1-0.5 ha. Rice crops were transplanted within a 14-d period. Management was left to the farmers.

Fish were stocked at densities of 60-200/ha. A mixture of *Cyprinus carpio* L. (common carp), *Tilapia nilotica* L. (*× mossambica*) (Nile tilapia), and *Puntius gonionotus* Bleeker (Thai silver barb) was used. The fish weighed 10-100 g.

The water depth was read at 2-d intervals from transplanting until weed density measurements at 40 d after transplanting (DT). We studied 6- or 12-m² sample plots, depending on field size, in each field. Plot area was reduced to 0.25 m² where plots had more than 1,000 plants/m². Weed plots were grouped according to average water depth. Weeds/plot were averaged for each weed group,

Number of weeds (+ SE) in different weed groups at 6 water depths. Ubon Province, Northeast Thailand, 1987 dry season.

Item	Weeds (no.) + SE											
	3 cm		5 cm		7 cm		9 cm		11 cm		13 cm	
Sedges												
Rice-fish	138	+ 44.2	106	+ 28.1	81	+59.6	60	+19.6	20	+ 6.5	15	+12.5
Control	184	+ 47.9	146	+ 36.8	63	+19.5	28	+ 8.6	7	+3.0	3	+ 2.2
Broad-leaved weeds (excluding <i>M. vaginalis</i> and <i>M. crenata</i>)												
Rice-fish	176	+ 49.6	60	+ 20.9	25	+11.0	170	+29.2	65	+42.3	3	+ 2.3
Control	170	+ 94.6	124	+ 23.5	100	+32.6	79	+40.9	9	+4.2	5	+ 2.1
Grasses												
Rice-fish	3.9	+ 1.92	2.7	+ 0.68	2.5	+ 0.87	1.4	+ 0.60	0.6	+0.60	0.0	+ 0.0
Control	2.1	+ 0.79	1.2	+ 0.46	0.6	+ 0.38	0.8	+ 0.22	0.2	+0.20	1.8	+ 0.47
<i>Monochoria vaginalis</i>												
Rice-fish	10.5	+ 4.37	14.6	+ 4.12	11.9	+ 6.19	16.3	+ 4.88	18.1	+6.50	14.6	+12.3
Control	9.8	+ 5.65	7.4	+ 1.74	10.8	+ 3.10	12.9	+ 3.86	3.8	+1.28	2.0	+ 1.41
<i>Marsilea crenata</i>												
Rice-fish	0.0	+ 0.00	0.0	+ 0.00	3.4	+ 1.93	20.7	+ 7.09	6.2	+5.55	11.4	+ 7.28
Control	29.6	+ 14.3	11.8	+ 5.87	5.7	+ 2.76	11.5	+ 3.85	11.8	+7.71	0.0	+ 0.00

Area (%) covered by non-algae weeds

Rice-fish	7.0	+ 1.60	3.3	+ 0.68	3.4	+ 0.67	5.9	+ 1.41	3.3	+1.19	2.4	+ 1.27
Control	5.0	+ 2.64	4.3	+ 2.45	3.1	+ 0.92	2.2	+ 0.88	0.4	+0.24	0.0	+ 0.00
Plots (no.)												
Rice-fish	13		26		10		21		10		8	
Control	11		20		19		20		5		4	

^aVillages of Kianjasoa, Mahasolo, and Tsiranomandidy.
^bVillages of Manjakandriana, Sambaina, Ambanitsena, and Miarina. ^cRanked fourth in Miarina, Central Highland.
^dRanked fourth in Sambaina, Central Highland, and fifth in Miarina, Central Highland.

treatment, and water depth class.

In control fields, sedges, broad-leaved weeds, and grasses were markedly reduced as water level increased (see table). Fish modified this general pattern by reducing sedges and broad-leaved weeds at low water depth (about 5 cm) when compared with the control. In contrast, fish enhanced weed growth at higher water depths. Similar results were obtained for *Marsilea crenata* and the percentage of area covered by non-algae

weeds. Results for grasses and *Monochoria vaginalis* are less conclusive, but show the same trend. Algae were reduced at 2, 6, 10, and 14 cm of water.

At 3 cm, the average number of uprooted sedges and broad-leaved weeds was 7.3/m² in rice - fish fields compared with 0.5/m² in controls; at 5 cm, it was 2.6/m² for rice - fish fields compared with 0.3/m² in controls. The results indicate that fish prefer shallow areas in ricefields

as a feeding place, possibly because food is more abundant there.

Fish affect ricefields in two major ways: their feeding activities reduce weed growth, and the accelerated turnover of organic matter enhances weed development. These feeding and fertilizing effects counteract each other. Water regime markedly influences the degree to which each effect operates. ■

Farming systems

Rice - wheat yields as affected by tillage and planting date

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We studied wheat yield productivity after the main crop of transplanted wet season (TWS) rice in West Bengal. Wheat was planted under irrigated conditions using different planting dates and numbers of tillages at the Agricultural University Farm during 1988-89 and 1989-90.

The rice - wheat rotation was laid out in a split-plot design with four replications, with tillage in main plots and planting date in 7.5 × 2.5-m subplots. Soil is medium fertile with pH 6.8, 0.061% total N, 7.4 kg available P/ha, and 141 kg available K/ha.

After the harvest of TWS IR36 rice, which yielded an average of 4.1 t grain/ha, fields were fertilized with 100-22-41.5 kg NPK/ha at the end of Oct. UP262 wheat was sown at 100 kg seed/ha in lines spaced at 25 cm on 1 Nov, 16 Nov, 1 Dec, and 16 Dec. Three tillage levels were used: zero - without plowing, but furrows for planting seed were made with hand tine; minimal - two plowings; and conventional - four plowings by bullock. Fertilizer was broadcast at sowing: 100 kg N, 22 kg P, and 41.5 kg K/ha from urea, single superphosphate, and muriate of potash, respectively. The wheat crops were harvested during the 1st, 2d, and 3d wk of Mar for 1st, 2d, and 3d and 4th planting dates, respectively.

The maximum grain yield of wheat was obtained from the 16 Nov planting and the

least from the 16 Dec planting. Wheat straw yields followed a similar trend (see figure).

Both wheat grain and straw yield increased with increased tillages, though yields under minimal tillage did not vary much compared with those under conventional tillage (see figure). Mid-Nov planting with either minimal or conventional tillage gave the maximum

wheat grain and straw yields after TWS rice (see figure). ■

Grain and straw yield of wheat as affected by planting date and number of tillages after transplanted wet rice. West Bengal, India, 1988-89, 1989-90 winter.

